

DUCTILE STEEL FIBER/EPOXY COMPOSITES WITH MODIFIED ADHESION

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1 Introduction

Structural fibre-reinforced polymers like carbon or glass fibre composites are limited to 1.5-4% of deformation before their final failure. This limitation is a result of the intrinsic brittleness of the reinforcing fibres. The composite strain-to-failure can be enhanced with the use of more ductile fibres, but most known ductile fibres such as polymeric and natural fibres are not stiff enough to compete with carbon and glass.

Fibres that simultaneously combine high stiffness and high strain-to-failure are difficult to find. A new type of fibres became recently available - steel fibres with stiffness of ~193 GPa, strain-to-failure of ~20% and diameter of 30 μm . Steel has a unique characteristic that its strain-to-failure can be altered using a heat treatment without affecting its stiffness. The previous research [1,2] has shown that composites made from these fibres possess a high stiffness and a high strain-to-failure. However, the full potential of 20% of strain has not yet been realized.

The purpose of the present study is to optimize properties of steel fiber composites by modifying the fibre/matrix adhesion. A higher adhesion may hinder development of matrix cracks and lead to a higher strength and strain-to-failure of a composite. In case of a too high adhesion, however, the cracks may result in localization and magnification of the strain, which is likely to cause earlier failure of the fibres. Thus, an optimal level of adhesion is sought.

For modification of the adhesion, different silane coupling agents are deposited on the fibre surface using wet chemical methods. Unidirectional (UD) and cross-ply (0,90)s laminates are produced using a vacuum assisted resin infusion process. The

produced composites are tested in a transverse 3-point bending test and under quasi static tensile loading to assess the effect of the adhesion modifications.

2 Materials and methodology

2.1 Raw materials

The annealed stainless steel fibres are supplied by NV Bekaert SA. They are woven in a quasi-unidirectional (Q-UD) structure consisting of steel fibre weft yarns and thin polyethylene terephthalate (PET) warp yarn (Fig. 1). The areal density of the weave is 1425 g/m². The steel fibres have a diameter of 30 μm and are made of a 316 stainless steel alloy.

The matrix is an Epikote 828LVEL (a Bisphenol-A type) epoxy resin with a 1,2-diaminocyclohexane (Dytek DCH-99) as hardener (15.2 / 100).

2.2 Modification of steel fibre surface

To modify the steel surface, silane coupling agents are used, which form a covalent chemical bridge between the steel surface and the epoxy matrix. The deposition is done by dipping the steel fibres into an alkoxysilane solution in a water/alcohol mixture. The alkoxysilane molecules in solution need to be sufficiently hydrolysed before they can attach to the steel surface by condensation of hydroxyl groups, while self-condensation in solution should be minimized (Fig. 2).

The silanes are shown in figure 3: 3-Aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APS) (a) and 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPS) (b) were purchased from Acros Organics, 1,2-bis(triethoxysilyl)ethane (BTSE) (c), acetic acid and

deuterated solvents for NMR measurements from Aldrich.

Before deposition of the silanes, the steel fibres were cleaned ultrasonically in ethanol for 15 minutes. After rinsing them in water and blow drying, the steel fibres were dipped in the alkoxy silane solutions and briefly rinsed in ethanol.

The APS solution was prepared from a 90/10 (v/v) water/ethanol mixture to which 2 v% silane was added. The GPS solution was prepared analogously, but the mixture was acidified with acetic acid up to pH 5. The BTSE solution was prepared starting from a 50/50 (v/v) water/ethanol mixture and also acidified with acetic acid. These solutions were stirred until maximum hydrolysis was reached.

After deposition, APS and GPS condensation to the substrate occurred by 4h of condensation in a vacuum oven at 90°C. In the case of combination with BTSE, the latter was first deposited on the substrate, dried for 1h at 90°C in a vacuum oven, after which APS was applied as described above.

With these coated fibres composites were produced within 1 hour after drying in the vacuum oven to eliminate aging effects.

2.3 Composite production

Three layers of the quasi UD structure were stacked for the UD laminate. Four layers were stacked for the cross-ply laminate in (0,90)_s. The composite plates were produced using a vacuum assisted resin infusion process. The impregnation was done at 40°C and the epoxy was cured for 1h at 70°C and post-cured for 1h at 150°C.

The produced laminates were investigated using optical microscopy and no voids or defects were found. Fibre volume fraction based on the thickness and areal density of the fabric was in case of the UD laminate $40.6 \pm 1.1\%$ and in case of the cross-ply laminate $38.4 \pm 1.3\%$. Figure 4 shows a cross-section of the UD laminate. The steel fibres are produced using bundle drawing, a process in which multiple fibres are combined in a copper matrix and further drawn to smaller diameters. Due to this process the fibres are packed in a hexagonal packing and this is largely retained when the copper is

removed. Due to this hexagonal packing, the fibre volume fraction within a yarn is on average $75.8 \pm 2.2\%$ (image analysis).

2.4 Experimental methodology

The transverse 3-point bending test was performed according to ASTM D790 on an Instron 4467. The test speed was 1 mm/min. Sample thickness and width were 1.5 mm and 10 mm, respectively, and the span was 50 mm.

The UD and cross-ply samples were additionally tested under quasi static tensile loading. The tests were performed according to ASTM D3039 on an Instron 4505. The displacement was controlled (2 mm/min) and the loading was measured using a 100 kN load cell. Sample thickness and width for the UD tensile samples were ± 1.5 mm and 15 mm, respectively, and for the cross-ply samples ± 2 mm and 25 mm, respectively. The gauge length was 150 mm and no end tabs were used.

The strains were measured using an optical extensometer. This technique uses a camera that takes digital images of the central region of the sample every 500 μ s during the test. Digital image correlation software Vic2D (LIMESS Messtechnik und Software GmbH) was used to calculate the average strain on the surface of the sample. The same images were used to observe the formation and growth of cracks on the specimen surface.

The damage development is additionally evaluated using acoustic emission registration. Two acoustic sensors (V5375-M) at the surface of the sample were used to detect sound waves, one at each end of the tensile sample. The energy of the AE events was recorded by VALLEN system and plotted as a function of strain.

2.5 Modelling methodology

An in-house developed software tool, WiseTex [3], is used to model the architecture of the quasi-UD woven fabric. The geometrical model is then transferred to TexComp software tool to predict the Young's modulus of the composite. The predictions are based on a homogenization technique, which employs the Eshelby solution and the Mori-Tanaka

assumption about inclusion interactions. The output of this model is used in the classical laminate theory to calculate the effect of the fibre alignment on composite stiffness. The properties of the constituent materials are taken as follows: stainless steel (Young's modulus (E) = 193 GPa, Poisson (ν) = 0,3), PET (E = 3 GPa, ν = 0,3), epoxy (E = 3 GPa, ν = 0,3). The fibre volume fraction is assumed to be 40%.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Transverse 3-point bending test results

The transverse 3-point bending test results show a significantly higher strength in case of the APS and GPS coatings (Fig. 5). The highest increase in strength, 46%, was measured in case of the GPS coating. The combination of BTSE and APS decreased the strength by 32%.

For further testing these two extremes (GPS and BTSE+APS) were used to analyse the influence of higher and lower adhesion strengths.

By optimizing the characteristics of the silane solutions and the dipping treatments these results can even be further improved depending on the outcome of the tensile tests.

3.2 Tensile test results: UD composite

Figure 6 shows the stress-strain curves of the tested UD specimens. The reference material shows a strain-to-failure of $14.1 \pm 1.5\%$. This is almost double compared to previous research [1] due to a different weave structure and about nine times higher than a typical UD carbon fibre composite and five times higher than a typical UD glass fibre composite. This shows that there is a huge potential to enhance the toughness of polymer composites by using steel fibres, since the full potential of the steel fibres (approx. 20%) is still not entirely realized.

The strain-to-failure of the reference is significantly higher than the strain-to-failure of the treated specimens. This is attributed to the misalignment of fibres that was introduced during the fibre surface treatment. During the treatment the Q-UD weave is deformed and this deformation results in a

misalignment, which can be up to 10° locally (Fig. 7). The treated samples are noted to fail earlier due to cracks starting from discontinued fibres at the sides of the samples. To properly assess the effect of the fibre/matrix adhesion on the composite tensile properties, the fibre misalignment needs to be eliminated. Further research is, thus, required to make definitive conclusions about the effect of the adhesion on composite strain-to-failure.

This local misalignment not only results in an earlier failure, but also in a lower stiffness (Fig. 8). The modelled stiffness is 78.9 GPa. When a misalignment of 5° is inserted in the model, the stiffness drops to 64.3 GPa. Comparing this with the experimentally measured values, it is likely that the misalignment is on average approx. 5° in case of the treated specimens.

While no conclusions can be drawn about the final failure, it can be noted that the yield strength of the GPS coated tensile specimens is significantly higher than that of the reference, which can be attributed to the higher adhesion as measured in the 3-point bending test (Fig. 8).

The effect of the misalignment can also be seen in the AE results (Fig. 9). The reference material shows a steep increase in cumulative acoustic energy while the coated specimens both show a more gradual increase. This can be due to the progressive failure occurring from the sides of the tensile samples. At the sides, steel yarns are cut due to their misalignment, cracks originate and grow parallel to the steel fibre yarns. This differs from the reference in which the failure is perpendicular to the loading direction (Fig. 10).

However, comparing the coated systems, it can be seen that the system with the lower adhesion (BTSE + APS) shows an even more gradual increase in cumulative acoustic energy. In case of the higher adhesion a more stepwise curve is recorded. It is thus possible that the higher adhesion delays the crack growth until a certain strain, after which the crack violently grows further.

From the observations it can be noted that modifying the surface influences the yield strength and the failure process of the UD tensile samples. However

due to the misalignment in the samples with treated fibres it is unclear whether a higher or lower adhesion is beneficial for the UD tensile behaviour.

3.3 Cross-ply tensile results

Figure 11 shows the stress-strain curves of the cross-ply samples. The reference material shows an average strain-to-failure of 17.4 % (at the time of writing only two samples were tested and as a result the 95% confidence interval is 15.4%). The strain-to-failure is expected to be in the same range as the UD tensile samples.

Similar as for the UD tensile samples, the coated samples show fibre misalignment, which is probably responsible for the earlier failure and lower stiffness (Fig. 12). It is, however, less pronounced due to the presence of the 90° layer. The modelled stiffness of the cross-ply laminate is 43.2 GPa. A 5° average misalignment decreases the modelled stiffness to 38.6 GPa.

The yield strength of the GPS coated sample is $\pm 10\%$ higher compared to the reference material (Fig. 12), which is also clearly visible on the stress-strain diagram (Fig. 11). This can be attributed to the higher adhesion in case of the GPS coating. Since the difference in yield strength is more pronounced than in case of the UD tensile samples, it is reasonable to assume that the strength of the 90° ply has increased significantly due to the GPS coating.

No real difference in yield strength could be found between the reference material and the BTSE + APS coating.

By using simple micromechanical models [1], the effect of the coating on the *in situ* behaviour of the 90° ply can be examined. This is done by assuming that the 0° and 90° ply do not influence each other and thus the isostrain assumption is valid. The *in situ* behaviour of the 90° ply can be found by subtracting a representative tensile curve of an UD composite (Fig 13) from the experimental tensile curve of the cross-ply composite.

In Fig.13 it can be seen that due to the GPS coating the 90° ply can reach higher stresses before transverse cracks occur. The BTSE+APS coated

material, on the other hand, has a lower stress in the *in situ* behaviour of the 90° ply. It appears that the lower adhesion due to the BTSE + APS coating lowers the strength of the 90° ply inside the composite.

In the acoustic emission results a similar trend can be seen (Fig. 14). The first events and first jumps to higher energy events occur at higher strains in case of the GPS coated samples, compared to the BTSE+APS coated samples. The BTSE+APS coated samples show a more gradual cumulative energy curve, which indicates a more gradual damage progression.

After about 1% strain the cumulative energy of the GPS coated samples surpasses the cumulative energy of the BTSE+APS coated samples. This is due to the higher stress build-up in the 90° plies of the GPS coated samples, which leads to higher strain energy releases when cracks are formed. This is confirmed by the *in situ* behaviour of the 90° plies because the stress for the GPS and BTSE+APS coated samples decreases with approximately the same rate after the peak stress. This means that more energy (stress times strain) needs to be released in case of the GPS coated samples

Similarly to the case of the UD tensile samples, the reference material shows a more steep increase in cumulative acoustic energy which can be attributed to the misalignment in the coated tensile samples. As a result, further research is needed to compare the behaviour of the reference material with the coated materials.

Figure 15 shows the surface of a reference tensile sample at different strain levels. Cracks are clearly visible and are homogeneously distributed over the entire surface. In further research these images will be compared to the different coatings to confirm the assumptions based on the acoustic emission results.

It can be concluded that the adhesion greatly influences the stress-strain behaviour of the composite through the behaviour of the 90° plies. Enhancing the adhesion ensures a higher *in situ* strength of the 90° ply and thus also a higher yield strength of the composite. Due to the fibre misalignment introduced during the fibre surface

treatment, it remains unclear whether the higher adhesion also increases the strength and strain-to-failure of the composite.

4 Conclusions

The results of this research show that annealed stainless steel fibres are a promising solution to enhance the toughness of polymer composites. The strain-to-failure of the produced composites is nine times higher than of a typical carbon fibre composite and five times higher than a typical glass fibre composite. The full potential of the steel fibres (~20% of strain to failure) is, however, not yet realized.

By modifying the surface of the steel fibres with different silane treatments, an increase of 50% and a decrease of 30% in transverse 3-point-bending strength can be realized. The modified fibre/matrix adhesion is found to have an influence on the yield strength and failure behaviour of the steel fibre composites.

Increasing the adhesion by 50% leads to a higher tensile yield strength in both the UD and cross-ply composites and a higher in-situ strength of the 90° plies.

Decreasing the adhesion by 30% does not have a clear influence on the tensile yield strength, but does decrease the strength of the 90° ply, resulting in a more gradual damage progression.

Further research is needed to investigate the influence of the adhesion on the strain-to-failure and the strength of the composite. An optimized fibre/matrix adhesion should ensure a full use of the toughness potential of the steel fibres.

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Fig. 1: Photograph of the quasi-unidirectional (Q-UD) woven structure

Fig. 2: (a) Alkoxy silane hydrolysis and self-condensation (b) Condensation to the surface

Fig. 3: Silanes used: APS (a), GPS (b) and BTSE (c)

Fig. 4: Optical microscopy image of the cross-section of a UD laminate

Fig. 5: Transverse 3-point-bending strength of steel fibre composites with different fibre surface treatments

Fig. 6: Normalized stress-strain curves of the UD tensile samples and 40 % of the steel fibre stress-strain curve

Fig. 7: Photograph of the local misalignment of the fibres on one of the treated specimens

	Reference	GPS	BTSE+APS
V_f (%)	40.6 ± 1.1	39.6 ± 0.9	36.6 ± 0.4
Stiffness	72.2 ± 2.6	63.0 ± 9.7	57.3 ± 2.2

[GPa]			
Yield strength [MPa]	172.6 ± 4.9	178.4 ± 6.6	159 ± 3.8
Normalized to $V_f = 40\%$			
Stiffness [GPa]	71.2 ± 1.1	63.7 ± 10.8	62.5 ± 2.0
Yield strength [MPa]	170.1 ± 1.2	180.2 ± 3.0	174.2 ± 2.2

Fig. 8: Experimentally measured stiffness and yield strength of the UD tensile samples

Fig. 9: Cumulative acoustic energy curves of the UD tensile samples

Fig. 10: Photograph of the difference in failure for a UD reference sample (top) and a UD coated (GPS) sample (bottom) due to the misalignment of the steel fibre yarns

Fig. 11: Normalized stress-strain curves of the cross-ply tensile samples

	Reference	GPS	BTSE+APS
V_f (%)	38.5 ± 0.6	36.4 ± 1.8	37.5 ± 1.2
Stiffness [GPa]	37.3 ± 0.3	33.3 ± 0.8	34.8 ± 2.3
Yield strength [MPa]	95.5 ± 8.1	99.7 ± 1.7	94.6 ± 1.6
Normalized to $V_f = 40\%$			
Stiffness [GPa]	38.7 ± 0.4	36.6 ± 1.1	37.1 ± 1.9
Yield strength [MPa]	99.1 ± 8.4	109.7 ± 4.8	101.0 ± 1.7

Fig. 12: Experimentally measured stiffness and yield strength of the cross-ply composites

Fig. 13: In situ tensile behaviour of the 90° plies inside the cross-ply laminates.

Fig. 14: Cumulative acoustic energy curves of the cross-ply composites under tensile loading

Fig. 15: Photographs of the surface of a cross-ply reference composite under tension at different strains

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